

Measuring The Impact Of Culturally Relevant Pedagogy On Students' Mathematics Performance

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 20 ,2025</p> <p>Accepted: August 20,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Mathematics Education, Culturally Relevant Pedagogy, Higher Education</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16913107</p>	<p><i>With the student population in America becoming more diverse, there is a growing need to not only close performance gaps, but to also develop pedagogies that reflect America's diversity. This study explored culturally relevant pedagogy's (CRP) impact on undergraduate students' mathematics performance. Specifically, the purpose of this study was to investigate changes in the mathematics performance scores of students of color and white students after participation in mathematics learning modules designed using a CRP framework. Furthermore, the study examined whether students preferred to learn with CRP or with traditional methods. This was achieved with an explanatory mixed method design. After experiencing the CRP learning modules, most participants exhibited performance gains, however, students of color showed higher gains than white participants. Also, all participants preferred to learn mathematics with CRP. These findings are important because they demonstrate how CRP can be utilized in mathematics and students of color can excel in mathematics. Future research directions are also offered, particularly, there is a need to validate these findings across a larger sample size and to understand in detail how students of color and white students' perceptions of CRP differed.</i></p>

Introduction

In United State of America (USA), many studies in the last 20 years have reported a mathematics performance disparity between students of color and their white counterparts. As the student population becomes more diverse in USA, there is a growing emphasis on addressing the performance disparities, a phenomenon referred to as "gap gazing" by Gutiérrez (2008). Gap gazing involves documenting gaps in academic performance between middle-class White students and those from historically marginalized groups, including Black, Latinx, First Nations, English language learners, and working-class students (Gutiérrez, 2008). Some scholars attribute several factors to this performance disparity, including racial discrimination from teachers (e.g., Alfaro et al., 2009; Levy et al., 2016; Pascoe & Richman, 2009); inequitable resources (Hursh, 2007); racist peers (Williams, 2011); socioeconomic status (SES) of their parents (Lee & Bowen 2006), and students' internalized beliefs of ability (e.g., Saphier, 2016).

Other scholars (e.g., Battey & Leyva, 2016; Powell & Frankenstein, 1997) argue mathematics is not culturally neutral. Instead, it is imbued with a pervasive Eurocentric bias that significantly impacts the performance of students of color. Given this bias, it becomes paramount for instruction to reflect various cultural and cognitive nuances that represent USA's diverse learners. Culturally relevant pedagogy (CRP) can potentially be that instructional method. Brown-Jeffy and Cooper (2011) view it as "a way for schools to acknowledge the home community culture of the students, and through sensitivity to cultural nuances integrate these cultural experiences, values, and understanding into the teaching and learning environment" (p.67). The purpose of this study is to examine changes in the mathematics performance scores of students of color and white students after participation in mathematics learning modules designed using a CRP framework. The study also aims to understand if and why students may prefer to learn mathematics with CRP or with traditional methods.

Literature Review

To understand the effects of Culturally Relevant Pedagogy (CRP) on students' mathematics performance, it is imperative to first understand the historical whiteness of American education, what CRP is, how CRP can improve learning and performance, and to identify the CRP models that can be used to develop mathematics learning modules.

Historical Whiteness of American Education

America's past is plagued with court cases (e.g., Brown v. Board of Education, 1954; Cisneros v. Corpus Christi Independent School District, 1970; Cumming v. Richmond County Board of Education, 1899;

Gong Lum v. Rice, 1927; Mendez v. Westminster School District of Orange County, 1946; Plessy v. Ferguson, 1896) that demonstrate the struggle of people of color to be included in America's educational system. From the time of the Civil War through the Civil Rights movements of the 1960s, the educational needs and cultural factors of diverse students were peripheral to white educators (Schmeichel, 2012). It is from this historical context that one can see how whiteness has pervaded educational institutions and curricula across a creolized U.S.A. Additionally, the domination of white curriculum has done double violence to students of color in that one culture was forced upon others and then the subjugation of students of color was forgotten (Bourdieu, 2003). That is, mathematical practices in other cultures were subjugated by white mathematical thinking and then educational institutions embraced and naturalized white mathematics to an extent that it is perceived as the only knowledge worth including in curricula. Barta and colleagues (2012) show that even students of color can believe that mathematics was created by and belongs to an external community that is different from their own. Rather than whiteness only, mathematics curricula should also represent Blackness, Latinxness, Native Americanness, and so on.

Culturally Relevant Pedagogy

Culturally relevant pedagogy (CRP) is a technique of infusing students' culture into teaching and learning. The technique has also been referred to as pedagogy that is "culturally congruent" (Au & Kawakami, 1994), "culturally responsive" (Gay, 2018), "culturally compatible" (Jacob & Jordan, 1987), and, more recently, "culturally sustaining" (Paris, 2012). However, the most common phrase is Ladson-Billings's (1995) term, "culturally relevant pedagogy." Gay (2018) defines CRP as teaching "to and through [students'] personal and cultural strengths, their intellectual capabilities, and their prior accomplishments" (p. 26); that is, CRP is founded on "close interactions among ethnic identity, cultural background, and student achievement" (p. 27). Ladson-Billings stresses that three principles must be satisfied before claiming successful implementation of CRP: (1) academic success must be observed; (2) cultural competence must be cultivated and conserved; and (3) critical consciousness must be fostered by encouraging students to critique the existing social order (Ladson-Billings, 2021). Here, critical consciousness is described as "the ability to recognize and analyze systems of inequality and the commitment to take action against these systems" (El-Amin et al., 2017, p. 18).

While there are many terms and conceptions of CRP, all the variations share a research-based teaching method and a thoughtful practice that upholds students' cultural and racial identities. This study uses CRP because, as Jackson (2021) explains, it focuses on a framework for teaching and learning of diverse learners. Furthermore, this study adds a concept called *centricity* (Tate, 1994). Asante (1991) explains centricity as "a perspective that involves locating students within the context of their own cultural references so that they can relate socially and psychologically to other culture perspectives" (p. 179). The strength of this concept lies in its ability to be universally applied across cultures. That is, the learning modules in this study aim to initiate communication from a student's familial cultural context and then build upon their existing thoughts. This can be achieved by incorporating culturally relevant topics that every student can relate to while mathematizing. In such a "centered" environment, each student is given the chance to understand the world through the experiences of others.

How Does CRP Affect Student Learning?

CRP was introduced to counteract the underachievement of disadvantaged and racial minority students in academics (Alismail, 2016; Bonner & Adams, 2012). Not only does it support academic achievement, but it is also known to support engagement (e.g., Byrd, 2016; Christianakis, 2011; Dickson et al., 2016; Rodriguez et al., 2004; Sleeter, 2012; Tate, 1995). For example, Rubel and Chu (2011) show that CRP affords students with the depth and breadth of opportunities to learn mathematics. In fact, their CRP model elucidated advanced cognitive demand tasks that enabled students to engage with mathematics at a deeper level and discover patterns across mathematics representations. CRP also creates vibrant classroom discourse where instructors do not dominate the conversation and students' cultural integrity is upheld (Bonner & Adams, 2012). It is these dynamic interactions that Bonner and Adams (2012) explain as contributors to their students' mathematics success. Through such interactions, positive student-teacher relationships are established, relationships critical in facilitating students' mathematics success (Jackson, 2013). Jackson suggested that, if instructors implement CRP successfully, then critical consciousness likely will manifest among students, a much desired outcome of CRP (Epstein et al., 2011; Martell, 2013; Morrell & Duncan-Andrade, 2002; Stovall, 2006).

Moreover, it is documented that CRP facilitates positive attitudes towards others as well as positive racial/ethnic identity affirmation (e.g., Aldana et al., 2012; Dessel et al., 2006). The CRP mathematics educators in Waddell (2014) expounded that CRP supports students to preserve their cultural identities as they pursue academic excellence. Furthermore, students tend to have positive learning experiences when taught with CRP. A study conducted by Hubert (2014) showed that all the students in his study preferred learning with CRP over traditional methods. These students also detailed that CRP improved their interest in mathematics. However, the major finding when discussing the effectiveness of CRP comes from Byrd (2016), who states that CRP is "...an important method for promoting achievement and positive identities for students of all races" (p. 7). This is noteworthy because of a popular misconception that only students of color or multilingual students need or

benefit from instruction being made culturally responsive, when that research points to a general benefit to all students when the status quo is challenged.

Models of CRP in Mathematics

There are variations on how CRP is conceptualized and defined in the field of mathematics (Harper, 2019). These models typically rely on Ladson-Billings' (1992) concepts of culturally relevant pedagogy, but not all of them incorporate Gay's (2000) concepts of culturally responsive teaching. Ladson-Billings' work focuses on broader pedagogical approaches, whereas Gay delves into the specific practical actions teachers should take. This study uses a Gay inspired model named culturally responsive science and mathematics teaching (CRSMT, Hernandez et al., 2013), to develop mathematics learning modules. CRSMT is selected because it is more comprehensive and it provides more specificity on how to operationalize CRP than the other models. The CRSMT model has five core principles: content integration, facilitating knowledge construction, prejudice reduction, social justice, and academic development.

Content integration refers to the addition of content from other cultures while holding high expectations and developing positive teacher-student relationships. Facilitating knowledge construction refers to learning by critiquing real world issues (especially issues students already know or can relate to) while maintaining independent thought. Prejudice reduction is achieved when there is a safe learning environment and positive student-student interactions are fostered. Social justice refers to teachers being agents of change that cultivate critical consciousness among their students by encouraging students to challenge the status quo. Academic development is the pursuit of academic success by using research-based instructional techniques that create learning opportunities for diverse learners.

The prejudice reduction principle is not present in the other models but is crucial because it stipulates "...methods for candidates to use in dealing with injustices when they encounter them in the schools" (Hernandez et al., 2013, p. 818). This kind of clarity in how to reduce prejudice is vital because racial minority students often experience microaggressions, stereotype threats, and other prejudices in their education (e.g., Tine & Gotlieb, 2013). Such experiences are known to negatively affect students' academic performance (e.g., Alfaro et al., 2009). Another principle that is critical but is not emphasized in the other models is social justice. Social justice is described as teachers' willingness "to act as agents of change" (Villegas & Lucas 2002, p.5) by inspiring students to challenge the status quo which then incites "the development of sociopolitical or critical consciousness" (Ladson-Billings, 1995, p. 483).

In conclusion, the review of the literature acknowledges that USA's reprehensible past is not divorced from the current academic performance of students of color. Contemporary educational inequities stem from early injustices "but are also augmented by present-day biases and systemic inadequacies that characterize everyday schooling..." (Marx & Larson, 2012, p. 261). The review also highlights that, in a nation with racially and culturally diverse learners, there is a pervasiveness of whiteness in mathematics curricula. Such a curriculum can academically delegitimize students of color and negatively affect their mathematics performance. This creates a need for a curriculum that captures students' cultures, interests, and life experiences. CRP could potentially be that curriculum and, while CRP models do exist, the development of more models is highly encouraged in mathematics (e.g., Brandt & Chernoff, 2014; Brown et al., 2019; Howard, 2021). This is especially true in college undergraduate mathematics (e.g., Brown et al., 2019; Jett, 2013) where no models were found, and the effectiveness of CRP has not been examined.

Methods

This study was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) and it aims to examine how CRP affects students' mathematics performance. In order to do so, three learning modules were created from Hernandez et al.'s (2013) CRSMT Model. The following research questions were the focus of the study:

1. How do participants' mathematics performance scores change after using CRP mathematics learning modules and how does that change appear among both students of color and white students?
2. Why would participants prefer, or not prefer, learning mathematics with CRP Learning Modules?

Study Design and Data Sources

The study used an explanatory mixed-methods design (Creswell, 2014) with one-group pretest-posttest research design (Bonate, 2000). The study unfolded in two distinct phases: quantitative then qualitative. In the quantitative phase, participants completed the pretest and posttest assessments, each consisting of 21 questions that were equally distributed between three topics (absolute value equations, systems of equations, and linear inequalities). The questions were selected from recent ACT exams that covered these topics and two independent experts cross-checked to ensure content validity and same rigor. Thus, participants underwent the pretest, engaged in three CRP learning module livestream sessions via Microsoft Teams, and concluded with the posttest. For the qualitative phase, data was collected through a Qualtrics online questionnaire to determine if (and why) participants prefer to learn mathematics with CRP or traditional methods. This questionnaire had three Likert scale questions and two open-ended queries. The Likert scale questions covered: relevance of

learned mathematics, likelihood of recommending CRP learning modules to a friend, and pace of the learning modules. The two open-ended questions asked participants about their reasons for choosing or not choosing to learn mathematics with the learning modules and how the learning modules were effective or ineffective in their learning process. Basic calculators were permitted during the study.

Participants

Participants were undergraduate beginning algebra students from a university in the Mountain West region. Students were screened for prerequisite knowledge (i.e., solving linear equations). Those that scored 70% or above on the screening test filled out a demographic survey and were invited via email to participate in the study. The score 70% is consistent with the university's recommendations for the required level of content knowledge to progress to a subsequent mathematics course. Twenty participants (10 students of color and 10 white participants) that passed the screening test were then randomly selected to participate in the study. The average age of the participants was 22 and all were fluent English speakers. Nineteen participants completed all parts of the study (one male student of color dropped out). Among the 19 participants, nine were male and 10 were female. Within the nine students of color, seven identified as Latinx and two identified as Black. The students of color sample and the white sample were representative of the university based on race, sex, socioeconomic status, and age.

Development and Implementation of the Learning Modules

The author created and served as the instructor for three learning modules that aligned with the CRSMT model. Learning module 1 covered linear inequalities, learning module 2 covered systems of equations, and learning module 3 covered absolute value equations. Each module included five main components: a pre-module discussion, peer introductions, topic introduction, practice problems, and a case study. With *centricity* in mind, the learning modules were designed to ensure that all students have multiple entry points based on their interests and cultures, thereby fostering a broader range of perspectives among them.

Pre-module discussion

Participants watched a short film on the use of Navajo language and culture in mathematics curriculum to show participants that mathematical knowledge is found in a particular people's sociocultural frame (Hernandez et al., 2013). The class discussed the film and the instructor also participated while encouraging independent thought and holding high-expectations for participation. The CRSMT model details that encouraging independent thought is one way of facilitating knowledge construction. Furthermore, the model details that creating a safe learning space by supporting self-expression is a critical part of content integration and prejudice reduction, especially when students experience positive interactions (Hernandez et al., 2013).

Peer-introductions

Peer introductions promoted positive teacher-student and student-student relationships, a safe learning environment, and were an important aspect of content integration and prejudice reduction. During this portion, the instructor hosted icebreakers for the first 10 minutes of each learning module and participated in these activities with participants. The icebreakers were games based on race and culture (retrieved from Clark, 2004) so that participants were comfortable discussing these issues (see Appendix A).

Topic introduction

During the 30 minute topic introduction, the instructor introduced new mathematics concepts by using culturally relevant real world examples. In learning module 1, the instructor used linear inequalities to compare the number of interracial marriages in the United States at different time points. The instructor then prompted participants to think about why interracial marriages have increased with time and how their own culture has changed through time to allow or disallow interracial marriages. The instructor also played the role of facilitator and employed techniques that allowed participants to discover algorithmic processes that were otherwise assumed to be standard. In the case of solving linear inequalities (learning module 1), participants completed a worksheet of problems to discover that dividing or multiplying both sides of an inequality by a negative number causes the direction of the inequality sign to change.

Practice problems

Practice problems provided fluency and reinforced conceptual understandings on topics covered in the learning modules. These were contextualized problems that connected to participants' daily lives. Participants worked individually first, then they gathered into groups of four with heterogeneous grouping configurations based on race. The instructor only assisted by providing hints and not full solutions. The goal was to allow collaborative learning and maintain high expectations through productive struggle and scaffolding for the participants. These notions are under content integration and academic development in the CRSMT model.

Case study

The modules included real-world cases that affected multiple racial demographics. Participants collaborated in groups for 30 minutes to grapple with a series of questions. In learning module 1, for example, the case study focused on gentrification and how it affects local communities and their cultures (see Appendix B). The groups watched a video illustrating gentrification then graphed, solved, and interpreted a model on gentrification. They also argued the benefits and drawbacks of gentrification in their local communities and

culture. The instructor acted as an agent of change by informing participants how to deter or encourage gentrification through their city councils. Appendix C and Appendix D show the case studies for learning module 2 and 3 respectively. These case studies promoted social justice by providing methods to question and challenge social issues (e.g., gentrification) as they occur in students' communities. The use of videos, group collaborations, real-world cases, and mathematical models were all learning opportunities that aligned with the CRSMT model.

Data Analysis

The first part of the analysis computed descriptive statistics and developed boxplots for the prescores, postscores, and change in scores. The researcher also used histograms to present each participants' prescore and postscore. The second part of the analysis used questionnaire responses to understand whether and why participants would choose to learn mathematics with CRP. The responses were analyzed through open, axial, and selective coding (Saldaña, 2015). Data analysis began only after conducting a screening test to ensure there were no significant performance gaps between students of color and white participants from the beginning.

Results

In the sections below, participants' performance scores and preferences for CRP are presented. All participants were given a pseudonym that uniquely identifies them. The pseudonym begins with the subgroup (SC-Student of Color or W-white) followed by their sex (M or F) and then a two-digit number. For example, WF02 would be a white female who was assigned the number 02, and SCM01 would be a student of color that is male and was assigned the number 01.

Overall Change in Scores after Using CRP Learning Modules

The first result focuses on overall changes in participants' mathematics performance scores after participating in the CRP mathematics learning modules. The researcher computed descriptive statistics for participants' prescores, postscores, and changes in scores. Table 1 demonstrates that the overall mean scores for all participants ($N = 19$) on the 21-question pretest and posttest improved from 45% to 59%, representing a change of 14%. Notably, both students of color and white participants exhibited improvements, with mean scores increasing from 45% to 66% and 46% to 52%, respectively. It is essential to highlight that students of color experienced the most change in scores, with an increase of 22%.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for Prescores, Postscores, and Change Scores

Variable	All ($N = 19$)			students of color ($n = 9$)			white ($n = 10$)		
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Range	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Range	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Range
Prescores	45	20	10-76	45	24	10-76	46	16	14-71
Postscores	59	18	28-86	66	16	43-86	52	17	29-81
Change scores	14	17	-19 – 38	22	13	-5 – 38	6	19	-19 – 29

Note. All numbers in the table are presented in percentages and are rounded.

Figure 1, a boxplot, visually demonstrates the improvement in participants' scores from the pretest to the posttest, indicating an overall increase in group scores. The improvement in scores between the pretest and posttest for all participants was statistically significant with paired samples *t*-test ($t(18) = 3.412$, $p = 0.00295$, Cohen's $d = 8$). This suggests that participants learned mathematics from the CRP modules to some extent.

Figure 1

Boxplots Comparing Prescores (Pre) and Postscores (Post) for All Participants.

Change in Scores by Subgroups after Using CRP Learning Modules

The next result focused on the differences in prescores and postscores among two subgroups: students of color and white participants. Figure 3 displays boxplots illustrating this comparison. It highlights a greater improvement in scores for students of color compared to their white peers, suggesting that students of color may have learned more from the CRP modules. An independent samples *t*-test ($t(17) = 2.172, p = 0.044$) also suggests students of color’s gains may have been significantly higher than those seen in white participants.

Figure 3

Pretest and Posttest Performance by Subgroup (Students of Color Pre/Postscores – ScPre/ScPost and White Pre/Postscores - WPre/Wpost).

Participant’s Preferences on CRP versus Traditional Methods

This section discusses qualitative results collected from a short questionnaire. The questionnaire had

three Likert scale questions on participants general experience and two open ended question on whether participants prefer learning mathematics with CRP and the perceived effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the CRP modules. Indeed, all participants preferred to learn mathematics using the CRP Learning modules over traditional teaching methods. Table 5 presents the results of the Likert scale questions.

Table 5

Summary of Responses from the Likert Scale Portion of the Questionnaire

Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. Did you find the mathematics to be relevant?	6	12	1	
2. I would recommend these Learning Modules to my friend who is learning mathematics?	10	9		
	Very Good	Good	Poor	Very Poor
3. How was the pace of the Learning Modules?	11	8		

The results of the open ended question were organized into two main themes: relevance, effectiveness, and positive learning experiences.

Relevance. Upon answering why participants preferred CRP over other methods, nine of the participants mentioned that CRP was more applicable to their lives than the mathematics they have seen in traditional classes. For example, WF02 (White) said, “I liked learning this way because it showed me how math is used in real life situations...it was nice to relate it [math] back to our life experiences.” Another participant, WM03 (White), recalled the case studies on gentrification, mental health, and medicinal marijuana and stated, “I would 100% choose to study using modules like these - they give me a REASON to care but other classes don’t.” On a similar note, WM04 (White) elaborated, “I would choose to use them so I can relate better to the math I’m learning. Most of the time you think that you will never use this outside of a math class, so what’s the point, but here it shows you how you can.” In general, this group of participants chose CRP because the mathematics under CRP was relevant to their life experiences.

Effectiveness. All participants, excluding WM01 (White), acknowledged the use of culturally relevant, real-world examples, as the most effective parts of the learning modules. WM01 (White) is the same participant, in Likert Scale Portion of the Questionnaire, that disagreed the learning modules were relevant. Participants that found the learning modules effective elaborated that real-world scenarios were only effective if they discussed issues they cared about and were complex. They explained topics like medicinal marijuana, mental health, or gentrification were complex because there was no definitive “right” answer and this was a welcomed challenge. WM03 (White) exemplified this sentiment by stating, “I don’t appreciate it when teachers give hard questions for no reason. The hard questions in the learning modules all had good reasons to be difficult - they were real.” SCF07 (Latinx) echoed this sentiment and even preferred to view the real-world problems as “world problems” that are nuanced by cultural contexts.

SCF02 (Latinx) identified real-world problems as being effective in supporting information retention. Three other participants validated this notion with WM06 (White) stating, “It [use of real-world problems] made the subject matter more memorable...definitely helps the learning process.” Several participants reported that culturally relevant real-world examples were effective in instilling confidence in their ability to transfer mathematical concepts to various contexts. Additionally, five participants appreciated how such examples were effective in supporting student engagement with mathematics. Furthermore, two participants valued real-world examples for exposing them to unfamiliar issues that they would not typically encounter. WM04 (White) explained:

I wish every class was like this, where...you introduce a real world issue or something that everyone can relate to, then figure it out. Not only just the math part of it or the science part of it or the English part of it... you [also] figure out the cultural part of it that’s going on. I think it’s going to make classes a lot more interesting.

However, one participant (WM01 - White) expressed dissatisfaction with the culturally relevant real-world applications, stating that they were less effective in improving his understanding relative to traditional

methods. Participants' descriptions of the real-world problems closely aligned with the critical elements of Culturally Relevant Pedagogy (CRP), fostering informative debates and reflecting individual cultural perspectives and interests. The real-world problems were crafted to address culturally relevant issues, leading participants to equate "real-world problems" with the concept of Culturally Relevant Pedagogy (CRP).

Positive learning experiences. 10 out of 19 participants stated that they would choose to learn with CRP because it was more enjoyable than other instructional methods. For example, WM05 (White), wrote, "I would choose these modules while learning math because the overall experience was super productive and enjoyable. I felt like I understood more because of the way everything was being taught." Another example is by SCM02 (Latinx), who wrote, "I would choose them [CRP modules] any day. The learning process is sensible, effective, and interesting. It was a class so complete and well planned that I felt happy just by learning." SCF01 (Black) identified another aspect that made the CRP modules enjoyable, she said, "I would choose to use these modules because I didn't think it was boring like a regular math class and I liked how interactive it was." There was a student (SCM01-Latinx), who had unique perspective, for him the ease of accessing the CRP module was the most pleasing aspect. SCM01 detailed, "I liked the availability of it. So I'd do it this way because I liked how easy it was for me to learn from them."

Therefore, it can be observed that the CRP Modules had a positive impact on participants' performance and preferences of learning. Participants demonstrated that they were able to learn and majority of them had positive reviews and a sense of enjoyment when they experienced the CRP modules. Particular to the questionnaire findings, participants perceived real-world examples to be effective when they were complex and centered around issues where their cultural perspectives and interests could be leveraged. Thus, suggesting that a CRP-focused approach enhanced the effectiveness of these examples.

Discussion and Future Directions

This study examined participants' performance scores and preferences after using CRP learning modules. Many participants improved in their performance and all the participants preferred CRP over traditional methods of instruction. However, in the absence of a control group, a limited sample size, and other confounding factors (e.g., the instructor's enthusiasm for CRP), the evaluation of the CRP modules can only suggest that some degree of learning occurred. That is, definitive conclusions regarding the exclusive influence of the CRP curriculum on the observed learning outcomes cannot be drawn. Instead, the results suggest that the intervention did not have detrimental effects, facilitated the acquisition of the targeted knowledge or skills as intended, and most importantly, CRP can effectively be integrated into mathematics instruction. These results are consistent with numerous studies reporting that CRP can successfully be implemented in the mathematics classroom (e.g., Aguirre & del Rosario Zavala, 2013; Hernandez et al. 2013; Jackson, 2013; Leonard & Moore, 2014; Tanase, 2020) and CRP can support academic achievement (e.g., Christianakis, 2011; Ensign, 2003; Gutstein, 2003; Rodriguez et al., 2004; Tate, 1995). Furthermore, the study shows that students can effectively learn essential mathematics concepts through culturally relevant mathematics curricula, especially in community college settings - an aspect relatively underrepresented in existing literature.

Due to students of color outperforming white participants, one could conclude that students of color learned more than their white peers in the CRP learning modules. This notion is counter to extensive literature that shows students of color with lower levels of performance in mathematics than their white peers (e.g., Snyder et al., 2016). Moreover, all the participants in this study preferred to learn mathematics with CRP over other traditional methods they have experienced before. Their preference for CRP was mostly attributed to the mathematics being relevant to their lives and the positive learning experiences they had. Preference for CRP is also documented in Hubert's (2014) study that involved African American students. The novel aspect of this study, however, is that even white participants preferred CRP over other methods of teaching and learning. Hubert's students stated that CRP supported them to learn beyond mathematics and here, as one student stated, CRP gave them a reason to care for mathematics. Another aspect of CRP that was enjoyed by some students were the discussions it sparked. Vibrant discussions are also observed in other implementations of CRP (e.g., Bonner & Adams, 2012).

The inclusion of students' cultural references in the modules supported mathematics learning, yet educators often refrain from using those references (e.g., Leonard & Moore, 2014; Simic-Muller et al., 2015). One reason for not practicing CRP is that many educators claim there are no CRP models to emulate in mathematics classrooms (Ukpokodu, 2011). This study offered a model, together with some specific examples, of culturally relevant topics that were meaningful to the students of color and white participants in the study. In essence, by also leveraging the concept of *centricity*, culturally relevant pedagogy (CRP) can integrate engaging topics with mathematics, ensuring that every student's cultural background is acknowledged without favoring one group over another. For instance, students of color initially perceived gentrification solely in urban contexts until a white student shared their experience of rural gentrification, recounting how his family was displaced to accommodate a new road. Conversely, white students were surprised to discover from a black student that mental health challenges in her family were often "prayed away". That is, students can bring a

variety of cultural perspectives to the same topic while mathematizing.

Given the findings of this study, it is still unknown whether there were whether positive student-student and teacher-student relationships, whether critical consciousness was developed, and whether there was prejudice reduction. It is also important to consider how the results of this study might be validated across a larger sample of participants, in a traditional face-to-face class, or with other institutions. With a larger sample size, the students of color group could be disaggregated to further explore performance differences between subgroups (e.g., Black versus Latino). In conclusion, current educational practices favor white students in their mathematics performance more than students of color. Pedagogy, being inherently embedded in culture, is already pertinent to certain racial, socioeconomic, and other demographic groups within the population. The critical question is not whether pedagogy is culturally relevant, but rather which segments of the population it caters to. Over years of data analysis, students of color have consistently exhibited lower mathematics performance compared to their white counterparts, despite being subjected to pedagogical methods that favor white students. This study highlights that when pedagogy is opened to a variety of cultural contexts, any performance disparity is effectively eliminated. Despite the myriad factors known to contribute to this performance gap, the CRP implemented in this study successfully bridged the gap. Furthermore, both students of color and white students expressed a preference for the CRP approach utilized in this study.

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